

Ferric-1-Hydroxyxanthone Complex: A Spectrophotometric Study

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Ferric-1-hydroxy xanthone system has been reinvestigated with a view to determine its suitability for spectrophotometric determination of iron (III). It has been found that between *pH* range 1.0 to 3.0, iron (III) forms only 1:1 complex with ligand, while earlier workers had reported the formation of 1:2 complex under these conditions. The optical density of the solution does not remain constant within any *pH* range and the method is, therefore, not suitable for spectrophotometric determination of iron as recommended by earlier workers. The equilibrium constant (K_1^*) of the complex has been found to be 44.2.

1-Hydroxy xanthone has been used as a reagent for gravimetric determination of uranium, thorium¹ and cerium(IV)² and spectrophotometric determination of iron(III)³. The stability constant of copper complex with 1-hydroxy xanthone has also been reported by Saxena and Seshadri⁴.

The present authors while determining the stability constants of some complexes of bivalent and trivalent metal ions with 1-hydroxy xanthone, found that the results for iron (III) complex are not in agreement with those reported by earlier workers³. These workers had reported the formation of a 1 : 2 complex of ferric iron with 1-hydroxy xanthone, whereas we could detect only 1 : 1 complex at all *pH* values. It has also been found that absorbance of the complex does not remain constant in the *pH* range 1.8—2.3 as was reported. For spectrophotometric determination of iron (III), these workers had used solutions of ferric perchlorate (obviously to avoid interference due to chloride ions), but subsequently the *pH* of the solutions was adjusted using hydrochloric acid, thus forming some chloro complexes of iron(III), in solution, which are yellow. They have considerable absorbance at 425 μ , the wavelength used by these authors for spectrophotometric study. In view of these facts it was thought worthwhile to reinvestigate the system with a view to determine the suitability of the reagent for spectrophotometric determination of iron(III).

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present investigations, solutions of ferric perchlorate have been used, but the presence of chloride ions or other complexing ions has been avoided by adjusting the *pH* of the solutions with perchloric acid or sodium hydroxide.

1. Brahm Dev and B. D. Jain, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1961, **54A**, 341.
2. Idem, *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 457.
3. Idem, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 247.
4. G. M. Saxena and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1957, **46A**, 218.

A Unicam spectrophotometer, SP 600, was used for taking spectrophotometric readings. Measurements of pH were carried out on a Metrohm pH -meter, E-350. 1-Hydroxy xanthone was prepared by the method of Desai et al⁵ and the purity of the ligand was checked by its m.p. and the technique of thin layer chromatography. The solution of the ligand was prepared in ethanol. Ferric perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolution of freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide in minimum amount of perchloric acid (E. Merck). The solution was standardised gravimetrically. pH of the solution was adjusted using dilute sodium hydroxide or perchloric acid. Ionic strength of the solutions was kept constant at 0.1M using sodium perchlorate (B.D.H.). All studies were carried out in 50% ethanolic medium as the ligand is insoluble in water.

Absorption spectra: Absorption spectra of the solutions containing iron(III) and 1-hydroxy xanthone in the ratio 1 : 4 were taken in the pH range 1.0 to 5.0, using ligand solutions at these pH values as blank. The complex was found to exhibit maximum absorbance at 420 and 580 $m\mu$. The absorbance of the system increases with increasing pH values upto 2.5 and decreases thereafter (Fig. 1). The molar composition of the complex was studied using the method of continuous variations. In the present study the maximum in Job's curves was found to be at 1 : 1 ratio at pH values 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 (Fig. 2). The absorbance values in all the Job's curves have been plotted after allowing for any absorbance due to ligand as well as Fe(III).

Fig. 1: Effect of pH on the absorbance of ferric-1-hydroxyxanthone complex. Fe^{3+} Concⁿ = $1.6 \times 10^{-4}M$; $HX = 6.4 \times 10^{-4}M$ Curve A at 420 $m\mu$; Curve B at 580 $m\mu$.

Equilibrium constant: Iron(III) reacts with 1-hydroxy xanthone according to the following equation:

$$K_1^* = \frac{[FeX^{2+}][H^+]}{[Fe^{3+}][HX]} \quad \dots (i)$$

The equilibrium constant of the complex, K_1^* , was determined at pH 1.0, as the complex hydrolyses at higher pH values. For this purpose, a series of solutions (in 50% ethanol) containing constant amount of 1-hydroxy xanthone and varying and excess amount of ferric iron were prepared. The concentration of perchloric acid in all the solutions was 0.1M to keep the ionic strength and $[H^+]$ concentration constant in these

solutions. The equilibrium constant was determined with the help of following equation:

$$\frac{1}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}]} = K_1^* \frac{C}{[\text{H}^+]} \frac{\epsilon}{A} - \frac{K_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{ii})$$

- [Fe³⁺] = Concentration of iron (III) ions,
- C = Total concentration of 1-hydroxy xanthone,
- ε = Molar extinction coefficient of the complex,
- A = Optical density of the complex (employing 1 cm. cells).

Fig. 2: Continuous variations method for finding the composition of Ferric-1-hydroxyxanthone complex.
 Curve 1, Total molarity=4.8×10⁻⁴M; pH 3.0; 460 mμ
 Curve 2, Total molarity=4.8×10⁻⁴M; pH 2.0, 460 mμ
 Curve 3, Total molarity=8×10⁻⁴M; pH 1.0, 420 mμ
 Curve 4, Total molarity=4.8×10⁻⁴M; pH 1.0, 540 mμ

Equation (ii) is derived from (i) as follows:

$$A = [\text{FeX}^{2+}] \cdot \epsilon$$

or $[\text{FeX}^{2+}] = \frac{A}{\epsilon}$

$$[\text{HX}] = C - \frac{A}{\epsilon}$$

or $K_1^* = \frac{\left[\frac{A}{\epsilon}\right] [\text{H}^+]}{\left[C - \frac{A}{\epsilon}\right] [\text{Fe}^{3+}]}$

By rearrangement of the above equation, we get

$$\frac{1}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}]} = \frac{K_1^* C}{[\text{H}^+]} \frac{\epsilon}{A} - \frac{K_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

By keeping $[H^+]$ and C constant, and plotting $1/A$ against $1/[H^+]$.. (Fig. 3), a straight line of $K_1^* C \epsilon / [H^+]$ slope and an intercept equal to $-K_1^* / [H^+]$ was obtained. Knowing $[H^+]$, the value of K_1^* was calculated to be 44.2. The value of ϵ was calculated from the slope as C , (H^+) and K_1^* are known and was found to be 1667 at 580 μ .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Iron(III) has been found to form 1:1 complex with 1-hydroxy xanthone at pH values ranging from 1.0 to 3.0, while earlier workers had reported the formation of 1 : 2 complex under these conditions. This discrepancy might be due to the fact that although they used solutions of iron, free from chloride ions, pH of the solutions was later adjusted with indefinite amounts of hydrochloric acid. The chloro complexes of $Fe(III)$ absorb appreciably at the wavelength used by these workers, which possibly led them to conclude the formation of 1 : 2 complex in the system.

Fig. 3. Determination of $\log K_1^*$ of ferric-1-hydroxyxanthone complex.

As regards the optical density at different pH values, it was reported by them that it is maximum and constant between pH 1.8—2.3. From Fig. 1, it can be seen that this is not the case if chloride free solutions be used. The curve shows that absorbance increases upto pH 2.5, above which it decreases apparently due to hydrolysis of the complex. Calculation of the extent of complex formation from the equilibrium constant, (at pH values from 1.8 to 2.3) shows that only 80-90% of iron is present in the complexed state. The method, therefore, cannot be considered satisfactory for spectrophotometric determination of iron as suggested by these workers.

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